

ROMANIA AND TÜRKIYE IN THE DYNAMICS OF EAST-WEST RELATIONS DURING THE COLD WAR. SECURITY PROJECTS IN THE BALKANS AND OFFICIAL MEETINGS, 1953-1989

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Abstract

The framework of bilateral relations between Romania and Türkiye during the Cold War was analysed taking into account the evolution of the international system and the ideological bipolarity of the two political-military alliances, to which the two states belonged. After Stalin's death, the withdrawal of Soviet troops from Romania, and Khrushchev's relative policy of détente, the establishment in Bucharest gradually began to build its own agenda abroad. It aimed at resuming relations with the West, especially in the economic area, and to assert itself internationally, by launching initiatives including in the field of security and cooperation in the Balkans.

The objectives of the Romanian officials have also found their counterpart in relations with Türkiye, which is also interested in reconsidering the relations with the US and its allies after the missile crisis and in prioritizing its own foreign interests. Particularly, after Nicolae Ceaușescu came to power, we witness a notable evolution of Romanian-Turkish relations maintained by a dynamic exchange of mutual visits starting from the level of heads of government (Maurer – Demirel), Foreign Ministers or those who held portfolios in the economic, technical, industrial, cultural and scientific area and up to head of state (Ceaușescu-Sunay), maintained until the second half of the 1980s. The constant development of the bilateral dialogue has been reflected in countless long-term agreements concluded between Romania and Türkiye at industrial, technical-scientific, cultural, commercial level, the establishment of joint economic commissions, but also in the progress made in the area of military cooperation, in the field of military industry and in the mutual support of security projects aimed at transforming the Balkans into an area of peace and good neighbourly relations.

Keywords: *Romania, Türkiye, mutual visits, cooperation, projects, regional security, Balkans, Corneliu Mănescu, Nicolae Ceaușescu, Süleyman Demirel, Cevdet Sunay*

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At the end of World War II, due to well-known political-ideological reasons, Romania's fate was sealed, becoming an integral part of the sphere of influence of the Soviet Union. The same course was followed by the other states in Eastern Central Europe, constrained both internally and externally by the Soviet hegemon: Albania, Bulgaria, Czechoslovakia, GDR, Poland, and Hungary.

Referring to the foreign policy actions of the states that entered the process of Sovietization, these were limited and conditioned by Moscow's desires and interests on the international stage. This involved freezing bilateral relations with Western states and imperative security measures, along with narratives condemning Western policies. Moreover, any foreign intentions, including visits between socialist bloc states, were carefully controlled and monitored by the USSR, which received detailed reports about their content and nature.

The new post-war geopolitical realities were reflected in the behaviour of democratic states grouped around the North Atlantic Alliance, which Türkiye also became a member of on February 18, 1952.

The division of Europe into two antagonistic political-military camps substantially affected the dynamics of international relations and the dimension of bilateral cooperation between states. Hence, in the first decade of the Cold War, Romanian-Turkish relations were even more sporadic and less documented in archives or historiography.

Even though after Stalin's death in March 1953, officials in Bucharest became interested in shaping their own foreign policy agenda and resuming relations with Western states, their actions were very modest. They were aware of the major dangers that could arise from an act of defiance. An essential role in re-establishing relations with Western states was played by Romania's admission to the United Nations structures on December 14, 1955, an event that facilitated affirmation and involvement in security and cooperation issues in Europe through initiatives and projects.

As early as the summer of 1957, discussions took place within the Political Bureau

of the Central Committee of the Romanian Workers' Party (PMR) regarding the possibility of launching a security project in the Balkans at the United Nations General Assembly. However, this was to be analysed with Soviet officials before proceeding. Shortly after, between August 15-16, a delegation led by Ion Gheorghe Maurer visited Moscow, where V.V. Kuznetsov¹ provided a positive response to the Romanian leaders, appreciating that their initiative "ensured security not only in this part of the world, in the Balkans, and in Europe, but also in Asia"².

The Romanian project aiming for the security of the Balkans was part of a broader plan to create a denuclearized zone in the region, consistently advocated during UN sessions and materialized in General Assembly resolutions such as 1236 (XII) "Peaceful and neighbourly relations among States" in 1957, 1301 (XIII) "Measures aimed at the implementation and promotion of peaceful and neighbourly relations among States" in 1958, or 2129(XX) "Actions on regional level with a view of improving good neighbourly relations among European States having different social and political systems" in 1965.

Romanian security initiatives in the Balkans received ample support from the Soviet Union, especially from a military strategic perspective. Nikita Khrushchev's promotion of the principle of peaceful coexistence led to changes in the approach to security and disarmament in relations with the West. However, developments in the Middle East, specifically the situation in Syria, an "ally" of Moscow in the Arab world, created tensions in Turkish-Soviet relations³.

In this context, a proposal for "improvement and development of relations between Balkan states" coming from an intermediary state, such as Romania, a satellite state, might have been better received by Western states than if the invitation had come directly from the Soviet hegemon. Thus, on September 10, 1957, before the UN session, Romania, through the voice of the Prime Minister of the Romanian People's Republic, Chivu Stoica, addressed a message to its counterparts

in Albania, Bulgaria, Greece, Yugoslavia, and Türkiye. The message extended an invitation to contribute to the “strengthening of friendship” and peace among the peoples of the Balkans⁴. Furthermore, Chivu Stoica’s call aimed at organizing a conference to develop a “collective understanding” to which states in the region, regardless of their political-ideological orientation, could adhere. This understanding would be based on principles of equality in rights, sovereignty, and non-interference in internal affairs, embodied through the conclusion of a treaty to transform the Balkans into a zone of peace. The response was favourable from the leaders of Yugoslavia (September 13), Bulgaria, and Albania (September 18). Greece gracefully declined the proposal (September 23)⁵, and Türkiye, as we will show, hesitated for years to take a stance on Romania’s initiatives in the Balkans. Indeed, given their ideological nature and NATO membership, the reactions of Türkiye and Greece did not surprise the political leadership in Bucharest.

On September 10, 1957, Romania’s representative, Chivu Stoica, sent a separate message to the Prime Minister of Türkiye, Adnan Menderes, expressing interest in the development and strengthening of Romanian-Turkish relations. This interest also extended to consolidating peace in the Balkans and peacefully resolving disputes⁶.

The documents from the National Archives and those of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, particularly telegrams and reports from the embassy in Ankara, reveal that the Turkish government had no reaction to the message from “Comrade President Chivu Stoica” regarding Balkan collaboration⁷, nor to subsequent invitations. This situation persisted until 1966, when Romanian diplomatic notes still mentioned that “as known, the Turkish government has not provided any official response to our initiatives from September 10, 1957, and June 5, 1959, regarding Balkan collaboration and the transformation of this region into a denuclearized zone”⁸.

Moreover, until Nicolae Ceaușescu came to power, Romanian-Turkish relations were characterized by the typical Cold War bloc rheto-

ric: mutual distrust, hesitation, suspicion, and the promotion of major powers’ interests at the expense of national ones. While a gradual opening towards the West occurred in Romania following the withdrawal of the Soviet troops in 1958, in Türkiye the economic crisis and measures adopted by the Adnan Menderes government heightened internal contradictions. The signing of a military agreement with the USA further inclined Türkiye to serve American interests, according to a note from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in 1959⁹.

The military coup in Türkiye in 1960, the return to a parliamentary regime, the rise of the İsmet İnönü government, the Cyprus crisis, and the missile crisis of 1962 were all events that led officials in Ankara to revise their foreign policy agenda. They were disillusioned and felt isolated from their alliance partners. Türkiye’s shift in its international arena also coincided with Romania’s interests, which aimed to build bilateral relationships with states outside the Warsaw Pact, particularly in the economic zone.

On February 11, 1961, Türkiye’s ambassador to Bucharest, İzzet Aksalur, in an audience with Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej, confirmed that “economic and cultural relations are developing well” between the two countries after the change of regime in Ankara and that he aimed to further enhance them. The Turkish official acknowledged the “economic momentum in the Romanian People’s Republic (RPR)” and appreciated the “friendly” attitude of the press and especially that of the Romanian authorities, who “welcomed him warmly”. Turkish delegations that visited the RPR “returned to Türkiye with the best impressions”¹⁰.

Regarding Romanian-Turkish political relations, the Turkish ambassador did not hesitate to mention that “the two countries have different socio-political regimes”: “Romania is a member of the Warsaw Treaty, and Türkiye is a member of NATO, and in these conditions, the two countries have important obligations to fulfil. In this situation, political issues can only be resolved in a comprehensive manner, addressing them as a whole and not on a regional level”¹¹.

Leader Gheorghiu-Dej supported the Turkish ambassador's opinions regarding the "progress" between the two countries in developing economic, trade, and cultural relations. He noted that "the mutual visits of delegations and personalities has contributed to strengthening relations", and that "the possibilities for developing relations between the Romanian People's Republic and Türkiye are much beyond the current level of relations"¹².

During the meeting, Gheorghiu-Dej brought up the Romanian government's proposals for creating a zone of peace in the Balkans, a solution to disputes among neighbouring countries. He also mentioned the convening of a conference to discuss matters of general interest, potentially resulting in an agreement to maintain peace in the Balkans. The leader from Bucharest highlighted the support received from the governments of Albania, Bulgaria, Yugoslavia, and the Soviet Union, which officially declared "its readiness, along with other major powers, to guarantee an agreement aimed at transforming the Balkans into a zone of peace". Furthermore, Gheorghiu-Dej informed the Turkish ambassador in Bucharest that during his visit to the United States, "some American circles view Romania's initiative positively", subtly indicating that "so far, no response has been received from Türkiye". However, the leadership of the Romanian People's Republic "is patient in this regard"¹³.

In conclusion, Ambassador Izzet Aksalur returned to the status of the two countries, stating that "they are part of two opposing military blocs" and that "the issue of maintaining peace in the world can only be resolved globally"¹⁴. This led to the assertion that "regional solutions cannot have an effect as long as major problems are not resolved on a global scale". Regarding Romania's expected response, the Turkish ambassador's justification implied that preparing a position for the government in Ankara stemmed from its "international commitments" (NATO membership). In the end, he stated that "it is good to wait for the results of the UN discussions"¹⁵. This referred to the 15th session of the General Assembly, where Romania's initiative was on the agenda,

indicating that Türkiye was not ready to have an individual stance and was waiting to adopt a bloc position.

In June 1962, Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej pointed out that Greece and Türkiye had a "negative attitude" towards Romania's initiatives at the UN and also towards proposals supported by the Soviet government regarding security in the Balkans and the Mediterranean¹⁶. Although Turkish officials had not officially provided a response recorded in Romanian archives, the authorities in Bucharest were aware of Türkiye's position based on its political-ideological affiliation. Hence, they sought to find common elements for cooperation in the economic sphere.

The final years of the Gheorghiu-Dej regime outlined a framework of Romanian-Turkish bilateral relations geared towards collaboration in trade, cultural¹⁷, sports, and scientific exchanges, through agreements, conventions, and more, which would be further embraced and developed during Nicolae Ceaușescu's era. An example in this regard was the Romanian proposal from November 1964, addressed to İsmet İnönü's Turkish government, suggesting the conclusion of a long-term economic (specifically commercial) cooperation agreement. However, it was not accepted on the grounds that Türkiye "was not yet in a position to move towards such extensive bilateral economic cooperation". This invitation was successfully revisited only in the following years¹⁸.

The year 1966 represents a key moment in the development of Romanian-Turkish bilateral relations, initiating a series of reciprocal visits that opened up new perspectives and fundamental changes in the dimensions of cooperation, consolidation, and partnership between the two states. The initial moment was marked by the visit of the Prime Minister of the Romanian Socialist Republic, Ion Gheorghe Maurer, to Türkiye (July 25-31, 1966), upon the invitation of his Turkish counterpart, Süleyman Demirel (extended on April 11, 1966). Subsequently, a year later, Süleyman Demirel¹⁹ visited Romania (September 11-17, 1967). This was followed by the visit of the Romanian

Minister of Foreign Affairs, Corneliu Mănescu, to Türkiye (November 24-26, 1968), against the backdrop of his popularity among the Ankara authorities, who supported his candidacy for the presidency of the UN General Assembly. Everything culminated with the visit of the President of the State Council of the Romanian Socialist Republic, Nicolae Ceaușescu, in 1969.

Returning to Gheorghe Maurer's visit to Türkiye from July 25 to 31, 1966, accompanied by Foreign Minister Corneliu Mănescu²⁰, which marked the upward trajectory of Romanian-Turkish bilateral relations, it is noteworthy that the visit was prepared to explore new possibilities of collaboration between the two states. Beyond economic subjects and the status of trade exchanges²¹, they discussed the political situation in Europe and the Balkan region, as well as disarmament and the prohibition of nuclear weapons. Maurer explained the "necessity of peaceful coexistence" among states with different socio-political systems and the establishment of a European security system²². Turkish Prime Minister S. Demirel, accompanied by the Turkish Foreign Minister during the Romanian-Turkish meeting, expressed interest in the proposals from the Bucharest delegation, stating that the importance of peaceful coexistence "must go beyond a mere statement of intention". This was a topic to which the Turkish government attributed significant importance in its foreign policy agenda, "unlike in the past".

Regarding Romania's initiative in the Balkans, Prime Minister Demirel "manifested an inclination to move beyond the initial position and consider the issue of establishing a European security system", showing interest in the "practical approach" to implementing this matter. Despite the nuanced changes highlighted in the Turkish Prime Minister's discourse on the dimension of the bilateral relationship with Romania, Ankara's "commitment to NATO" was not forgotten, framed within a "collective defence system" due to the "threat materialized by the territorial claims of the Soviet Union over two eastern provinces of Türkiye"²³.

The Turkish Prime Minister's conclusion was that, despite a "certain mutually advantageous approach" with Moscow and an inten-

tion for collaboration, he could not help but reiterate an older position that "security in a specific region is not valuable as long as security is not achieved worldwide"²⁴.

The visit of the Romanian government delegation to Türkiye marked the first extensive bilateral contact between the two states, where the complex issues of European security were discussed. This led to the conclusion of new agreements in the fields of science, arts, tourism, as well as the initiation of negotiations on maritime navigation and other economic domains²⁵.

At the invitation of the Romanian side, on September 11-17, 1967, the Prime Minister of Türkiye, Süleyman Demirel, visited Romania, during which the security issues in the Balkans were revisited, which were the basis for Romanian initiatives supported at the UN sessions. The year 1967 was particularly significant for the establishment in Bucharest, as Romania's Minister of Foreign Affairs, Corneliu Mănescu, successfully ran for the presidency of the UN General Assembly. He became the first Romanian to be elected to this position on October 19, 1967, by 112 out of a total of 120 states. Türkiye was among the states that voted in favour.

From the beginning of the year, on February 25, 1967, in a note proposing a visit to Romania by a delegation led by Süleyman Demirel, the Turkish side responded "positively and promptly" to the Romanian request to support Corneliu Mănescu's candidacy for the presidency of the twenty-second session of the UN General Assembly²⁶.

The support for Mănescu by Türkiye²⁷ marked the positive outcome of the course of Romanian-Turkish relations, amid the development of contacts at the level of government leaders and foreign ministers. Also in 1967, in the second half of May, I.S. Çağlayangil, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Türkiye, visited Romania²⁸ to examine the progress of resolving the issues discussed with Prime Minister Maurer in Türkiye and the possibility of signing consular and legal assistance conventions²⁹, as well as new agreements in tourism, air, road, and maritime transportation, among others³⁰. However, the most significant aspect that

emerged during the visit of the Turkish diplomat Çağlayangil to Romania was his admission that “the membership of Balkan countries in different socio-political systems does not constitute an obstacle to the normal development of relations between them”. This statement carried significant weight in the development of Romanian-Turkish relations at the highest political level, highlighting Türkiye’s desire to open up new perspectives for cooperation in the Balkans³¹.

The evolution of Romanian-Turkish relations was noted during the visit of Turkish Prime Minister Süleyman Demirel to Romania in the autumn of 1967, accompanied by the Foreign Minister, I.S. Çağlayangil, who was visiting Bucharest for the second time that year.

During the discussions, the Turkish Prime Minister officially explained why Türkiye did not respond to the proposals made by the President of the Council of Ministers of the Romanian People’s Republic in 1957 and also remained silent on those from 1959. He stated that, until 1964, “Turkish statesmen did not refer in their statements to the issue of Balkan collaboration”. Modest progress appeared a year later at the United Nations General Assembly when Foreign Minister Çağlayangil declared that “establishing friendly relations between Türkiye and the other Balkan countries would contribute to consolidating peace and promoting cooperation in our Balkan region”³². This aspect was also noted in the documentary records of Romanian diplomats in 1967, reporting that Demirel’s government program was aimed at expanding foreign relations with socialist states and achieving “greater independence from the USA and NATO”. This suggests that Türkiye was beginning to adopt its own position on international issues³³.

Moreover, starting in the fall of 1967, we observe substantial changes in the discourse of Turkish officials. If, up to that point, the government justified its position through its membership in NATO, within the framework of a collective defence system, Süleyman Demirel changed the paradigm, stating that “countries will be entitled to seek security in a regional framework” as long as they cannot be

protected within the UN. However, in the end, he makes a veiled mention of NATO membership obligations stemming from Türkiye’s strategic and geographic position³⁴.

Interestingly to note in the dynamics of Romanian-Turkish relations was the appearance in the pro-government newspaper “Zafer” on August 24, 1967, of an editorial by former ambassador to Bucharest, C.T. Karasapan, which highlighted the Romanian proposals for collaboration among the Balkan states from the late 1950s, “which did not resonate in Ankara at that time”³⁵.

Later on, we can observe that Türkiye’s relations with socialist states entered a new phase, in which the government in Ankara aimed “to develop [them] harmoniously, in a spirit of neighbourliness”, through reciprocal visits, including with the Soviet Union, even if, in fact, economic collaboration was paramount³⁶.

During the exchange of talks that took place in the autumn of 1967 between the two Romanian and Turkish delegations, Prime Minister Ion Gheorghe Maurer reiterated that Romania attaches great importance to creating an atmosphere of understanding and good neighbourliness in the Balkans. He considered that the highly positive development of friendly relations between Romania and Türkiye, countries with different social-political systems, represents a significant contribution in this direction³⁷. In turn, Turkish Prime Minister Demirel emphasized during the visit that the Turkish government is making efforts to establish good neighbourly relations in the Balkans, highlighting the rapid development of relations between the two states, especially in the economic, social, and cultural domains³⁸.

From November 24-26, 1968, Foreign Minister Corneliu Mănescu made another visit to Türkiye, emphasizing the need for new opportunities to develop bilateral relations and new actions and exchanges of views regarding Balkan collaboration³⁹. The main proposal was to organize a meeting of the foreign ministers of the countries in the geographical region of the Balkans⁴⁰. The Romanian official was well received by the government in Ankara, especially given his popularity for his actions at the

**Nicolae Ceaușescu bidding farewell to the President of the Republic of Türkiye,
General Cevdet Sunay (March 29, 1969, Esenboga Airport)**

Source: "Fototeca online a comunismului românesc", reference number: 14/1969

UN. The results of the bilateral meeting were favourable for both parties, and the visit, as always, provided an opportunity to conclude new conventions and agreements in the economic domain. The visit of the Romanian Foreign Minister was also conducive to organizing and arranging the visit of the President of the State Council, Nicolae Ceaușescu, to Türkiye⁴¹.

Following this, from March 24-29, 1969, Nicolae Ceaușescu and his wife Elena made another visit to Türkiye (Ankara, Istanbul, and Izmir) at the invitation of counterpart Cevdet Sunay. The visit represented a landmark moment in the history of Romanian-Turkish relations after Romania's proclamation of independence in May 1877, particularly during Nicolae Ceaușescu's era. After the meeting

between the two heads of state, fruitful Romanian-Turkish collaboration ensued, supported by new reciprocal visits over two decades, an acceleration of the regulation of bilateral relations through a huge series of agreements in all fields, although the most important dimension remained consistently economic, followed by trade.

An important area in which "fruitful collaboration" was sought was the "improvement of the peace climate" in the Balkans, an obsessive theme on Nicolae Ceaușescu's foreign policy agenda. "I believe that no effort is too great to make the Balkans a zone of good neighbourliness and fruitful collaboration", stated the Romanian official in his first speech at Ankara on March 24, 1969, during the dinner

hosted by Sunay⁴². In his interventions during the visit, Ceaușescu highlighted the “positive evolution of relations between Romania and Türkiye”, demonstrating “convincingly that differences in societal organization are not an impediment”. He emphasized that ensuring peace and security “does not go through the division of the world into opposing military blocs but through collaboration” between states⁴³. Demirel, in turn, assured that Türkiye’s foreign policy is intended to contribute to the defence of peace and the improvement of the climate in the Balkans, emphasizing that “there are possibilities” for Romanian-Turkish relations “to develop even further, as well as to establish contacts in other areas”. Economic cooperation and agreements in trade, tourism, transportation, consular relations, and legal assistance were already appreciated⁴⁴. At the end of the visit, the joint Romanian-Turkish statement stated that the constructive contri-

bution of bilateral relations between the two states would positively influence the situation in the Balkans. The two leaders shared common beliefs regarding nuclear disarmament and the peaceful resolution of tensions⁴⁵.

Furthermore, in interviews with the newspaper “Scântea” during President Ceaușescu’s visit to Türkiye, Cevdet Sunay emphasized that there was “full agreement for the development and diversification of relations between Romania and Türkiye”, and “there is no problem to be settled”⁴⁶. This provided an open path towards bilateral collaboration in all areas. Supporting this initiative, S. Demirel added that Türkiye’s “open and fair” policy was directed towards peaceful coexistence and collaboration with both large and small states, aiming to serve mutual interests⁴⁷. Demirel concluded that Romanian-Turkish relations had seen significant development and represented “the most beautiful proof that belonging to different allian-

**Nicolae Ceaușescu welcoming the President of the Republic of Türkiye,
General Cevdet Sunay (April 13, 1970, Bucharest-Otopeni International Airport)**

Source: "Fototeca online a comunismului românesc", reference number: 15/1970

es and having different social systems do not constitute an obstacle to mutual development”.

On April 13-17, 1970, President Cevdet Sunay accepted the invitation from his counterpart Nicolae Ceaușescu to visit Romania, touring cities like Bucharest, Craiova, Constanța, the Black Sea coast, and the hydroelectric plant on the Argeș River. He acknowledged the nature of the Romanian-Turkish bilateral relations, which had reached their peak with the Romanian leader's visit to Türkiye a year prior. The significance of the visit was emphasized by the signing of an agreement between the Romanian and Turkish governments to establish a joint economic commission aimed at intensifying economic, industrial, and technical cooperation between the two states⁴⁸. The issue of security remained a constant in the messages of the two leaders, reiterating their mutual beliefs in supporting any realistic initiative for good neighbourly relations among Balkan states⁴⁹, based on principles of equality, non-interference in internal affairs, and the avoidance of the use of force.

In the early 1970s, against the backdrop of international developments and a climate of détente in relations between the USA and the Soviet Union, Western states became increasingly interested in Romania's foreign policy. A particular aspect was the growing number of reciprocated visits⁵⁰. In American diplomats' notes, Nicolae Ceaușescu was appreciated as a “maverick” within the Eastern bloc, especially after publicly condemning the Warsaw Pact troops' invasion of Czechoslovakia in 1968. Moreover, Romania's openness to the West, its affirmation within CSCE meetings through security and disarmament initiatives like reducing nuclear weapons, and the aspiration to transform the Balkans into a zone of peace, were actions that gave the Romanian dictator a significant image capital in the West⁵¹.

On July 30, 1971, a telegram from the Romanian embassy in the USSR stated that the US State Department had received information suggesting a conference of the Warsaw Pact states was to be convened to discuss European security issues and aspects of relations among the Balkan countries. American diplo-

mats in Moscow hinted that during this meeting (about which their Romanian counterparts had not been informed), “issues related to the visit of the Romanian party and government delegation to China were to be raised, which had caused dissatisfaction among the other socialist countries of the Warsaw Pact”⁵².

The tension in relations between the Romanian leader and the socialist bloc was reflected in documents from Bulgarian archives after the meeting in Crimea on August 2, 1971: “indeed, a series of opinions were expressed regarding the existing differences with the Romanian communist leader, Nicolae Ceaușescu”⁵³. After returning from Yalta, Todor Zhivkov, the President of the State Council of Bulgaria, informed his colleagues about Moscow's concern that, “by aligning among themselves and with China”, Yugoslavia, Romania, and Albania could form a distinct group in the Balkans that could “openly or secretly” create a regional Balkan bloc “based on anti-Sovietism”. In Leonid Brezhnev's opinion, the leader of Moscow, “Ceaușescu has gone too far”, which is why serious discussions were scheduled with him to make “the Romanians realize that their actions are wrong and dangerous”⁵⁴.

Indeed, a key aspect in Romania's relations with members of the Warsaw Pact was the Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe, which represented one of the best opportunities for the leadership in Bucharest to assert itself on the international stage, expose its own foreign policy line, and free itself from Soviet pressure. Consistently, through the initiatives of the establishment in Bucharest to address security and other issues outside the patterns imposed within the socialist political-military bloc, Romania and Ceaușescu were in the spotlight of criticism from Leonid Brezhnev. However, the Soviet leader limited himself to such verbal observations, which weighed heavily in the analysis of international relations. Romania's behaviour was not sanctioned within the meetings of the Warsaw Pact because the Soviet Union had an interest in maintaining an atmosphere of fair play among socialist states while presenting a bloc posi-

tion, especially on security issues, to Western audiences.

Inaugurated in Helsinki on November 22, 1972, the preliminary conference on European security was a success for Moscow's diplomacy. In January 1973, in a summary of the discussions held by the USSR leader with the Ministers of Foreign Affairs regarding the progress of negotiations with Westerners, Leonid Brezhnev remarked, "we could turn the world upside down in just one year, we, the socialists"⁵⁵, emphasizing that the success was due to the joint action of the member states of the Warsaw Pact.

At the end of the reunion, Brezhnev did not fail to point out, once again, that "it was not helpful when the Romanians in Helsinki entered into discussions on unimportant matters"⁵⁶, classified as "trifles" that could lead to postponing the CSCE process. The Soviet leader's reactions oscillated between calling for bloc unity and constant reprimands of Ceaușescu, often invoked in discussions with other socialist counterparts: "I told Ceaușescu [...] the Westerners are just waiting for us to falter and give them pretexts to postpone everything. [...] We must work together. If cracks appear, then we will have difficulties"⁵⁷.

Romania continued to pursue its own course in relations with the Western world and Türkiye, aiming to develop economic relations, acquire technologies and licenses, without "escaping" from the socialist bloc. Romania was aware of the importance of maintaining a status quo in its relationship with Moscow and the Eastern states.

In the first half of the 1970s, Romanian-Turkish cooperation continued to be constructive for both states, through the signing of new economic and trade agreements, technical-scientific and cultural agreements. On March 26, 1971, a new government led by İsmail Nihat Erim was installed in Ankara. Between November 3-7, 1971, Corneliu Mănescu, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Socialist Republic of Romania, made another official visit to Türkiye, during which he reported that against a backdrop of détente, the Erim government continued "to contribute and support any constructive proposal" aimed

at serving peace in the Balkans. Mănescu reported that the Romanian delegation was received "with great attention and cordiality"⁵⁸.

On March 21, 1972, a note signed by Romania's ambassador to Ankara, George Marin, pointed out that there were new developments in Türkiye's attitude regarding collaboration in the Balkans: "new, positive qualitative nuances"⁵⁹. This change in the Ankara government was determined by the policy of the major powers, which, in the interest of solving global problems, "can neglect small countries, even when they are part of the same military alliances"⁶⁰. Furthermore, this political conviction was also shared by the leadership in Bucharest about the Eastern alliance to which Romania belonged, a common element that brought Romania and Türkiye even closer. The Ankara government noted the "reduction of the strategic interest of the USA in Türkiye" by choosing Greece to build a base for the Sixth Fleet, a signal that undermined the Turks' trust and collaboration with NATO. Meanwhile, Türkiye offered assurances that it makes "efforts to maintain friendly relations with neighbouring countries"; which was a reality, launching a series of invitations, including visits to Yugoslavia, Bulgaria, and Greece⁶¹. The Bulgarian side proved to be the least cooperative, refusing the possibility of a bilateral meeting⁶², while the Greek authorities engaged in several bilateral contacts, albeit against the backdrop of NATO membership.

Starting in 1973, from the contacts between the Romanian ambassador and military attaché in Ankara and Turkish officials, we can discern the mutual desire to develop bilateral relations, including in the military domain. Initially, opportunities for development in military education emerged, with exchange visits between naval training ships, meetings between military sports teams⁶³, and later, in early 1974, the first tentative talks at the level of Defence Ministers. Ion Ioniță, the Romanian Minister of Defence, extended an invitation to his Turkish counterpart, Hasan Esatışik, to make an official visit to Romania⁶⁴.

After the adoption of the Helsinki Final Act in August 1975, which, among other things, provided for order and security on the Europe-

an continent based on principles of sovereign equality of states, non-use of force or threat of force, and cooperation between states, a new series of reciprocal visits was recorded in Romanian-Turkish relations.

On August 27-29, 1975, President Süleyman Demirel made another visit to Romania at the invitation of his counterpart, Nicolae Ceaușescu. During the meetings, the two heads of state exchanged views on the conclusion of the CSCE conference in Helsinki, concluding on an optimistic note that it would have reverberations on establishing real peace in the Balkans⁶⁵. The leader of the Romanian Socialist Republic also argued that expanding cooperation among Balkan states in different areas would transform the region into one devoid of nuclear weapons, military troops, and foreign bases. The President of Türkiye approved the statements made by his counterpart, stating that the development of Romanian-Turkish relations was not only in the interest of both countries, but also for security in the Balkans. The good collaboration was seen from a “long-term perspective”⁶⁶.

Less than a year later, on June 22, 1976, Nicolae Ceaușescu visited Türkiye once again for four days at the invitation of the new Turkish president, Fahri Korutürk. The newspaper “Scântea” stated on the front page of June 23, 1976, that the visit of the Romanian dictator to Türkiye represented a “new impetus” and “a new and significant moment in Romanian-Turkish dialogue at the highest level”, emphasizing the common desire of the two countries “to contribute to the strengthening of peace, security, and cooperation in the Balkans”⁶⁷. The issue of security in the Balkans became more present and obsessive than ever in Ceaușescu’s discourse, with the official stating that Romania, like Türkiye and other countries in the Balkans and Europe, was “deeply interested in the Mediterranean, the Aegean, and the Black Sea to be dominated by understanding and security”, and the seas should become “those of peace and collaboration”⁶⁸. The issue of disarmament was not forgotten, and the desire was for the Balkans to be devoid of nuclear weapons, troops, and military bases⁶⁹.

On August 3, 1976, a meeting took place in Yalta, Crimea, between Nicolae Ceaușescu, the General Secretary of the Romanian Communist Party, and Leonid Brezhnev, the General Secretary of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, regarding the perspectives of collaboration among Balkan states. The Soviet leader explained to his Romanian counterpart that “raising the issue of a Balkan union or alliance has no solid basis”⁷⁰ because Türkiye and Greece were part of NATO. “Such a union has no justification”, said Brezhnev, other than Ceaușescu’s “desire” to have “something” in the Balkans⁷¹.

Nicolae Ceaușescu offered a detailed response, arguing that “the problem is not understood correctly”: “First of all, no one raises the issue of a Balkan union. This would be entirely unrealistic. Secondly, improving relations and developing collaboration between Balkan countries is not only in the interest of the Balkan countries but also of socialist countries, I could say even in the interest of the Soviet Union”⁷². Nicolae Ceaușescu also mentioned the transportation routes in the Balkans, “which could not be ensured through Bulgaria, Romania, Türkiye, Greece, or Yugoslavia”, adding that it was “in everyone’s interest to solve certain problems of this kind”. The Romanian official asked Brezhnev what the socialist countries had to lose. The Soviet counterpart manifested irritation with how Bucharest handled the situation, especially in its relationship with the West: “You raise the issue of expanding and deepening regional collaboration in the Balkans”⁷³.

During March 21-23, 1977, George Măcovescu, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Socialist Republic of Romania (RSR), visited Türkiye to meet his Turkish counterpart, İ.S. Çağlayangil. The discussions covered various topics, including the positive outcome of Ceaușescu’s visit to Türkiye and the successful collaboration between Romanian and Turkish delegations in the CSCE, particularly concerning economic aspects⁷⁴. A key issue analysed in the context of Balkan security was Bulgaria’s negative stance towards collaboration with Türkiye. In this regard, the Turkish leadership expressed concerns about the USSR’s position

on Balkan cooperation, especially economic, which they were going to discuss during the Turkish foreign minister's upcoming visit to Moscow⁷⁵. At the end of George Macoveșcu's visit to Türkiye, following an agenda set by Nicolae Ceaușescu, especially focusing on regional security, the Romanian and Turkish delegations concluded that "there are ample opportunities for political cooperation in the Balkans"⁷⁶.

Nicolae Ceaușescu's persistence in reacting to the Balkan situation often perturbed Leonid Brezhnev. During the meeting on August 14, 1978, in Yalta, the Soviet leader confided to his trusted ally, Bulgarian leader Todor Zhivkov, that the relationship with the Romanian dictator was "agitated". The essence of the Soviet attitude towards this situation can be summarized as follows: "I know, Todor, that you've had several opportunities to speak directly and frankly with Ceaușescu. It's clear that the necessity for such influence is now extremely important", Brezhnev stated⁷⁷. The policy promoted by Romanian officials regarding Balkan cooperation created "diplomatic complications for Bulgaria: «When they stir up the issue of establishing Balkan cooperation, they do it simply on a whim»". From Brezhnev's perspective, the issue of regional cooperation in the Balkans, as seen by Romanians, Yugoslavs, and Greeks, was a way to reduce the influence of the Warsaw Pact states in the region. This was the essence of their approach. Brezhnev recommended "countering decisively all projects aimed at creating an autonomous Balkan group to promote «their particular interests»"⁷⁸.

During this period, new details emerged regarding the prospects of Romanian-Turkish relations, particularly in the military domain. Hasan Işık, the Turkish Minister of National Defence, positively assessed the state of bilateral collaboration, proposing that the Romanian side "prepare to discuss possibilities for mutual supply of materials necessary for the army" and cooperate in "building industrial facilities in Türkiye to produce technical means necessary for the army and which could be exported to Romania and other countries".

In the conversation with Romanian ambassador George Marin, Hasan Işık explained that part of the army's necessary imports were to be "paid for by deliveries of military materials produced in Türkiye". These Turkish proposals were to be discussed with the Romanian side during meetings with Ion Hortopan, the Deputy Minister of National Defence and Chief of the General Staff, and possibly with Minister Ion Coman, who had received invitations to visit Ankara⁷⁹. During protocol actions with Romanian diplomats on August 1, 1978, General Kenan Evren, the Chief of the General Staff of the Turkish Army, emphasized the interest in Romania's foreign policy in the Balkans and relations with neighbouring countries. Taking advantage of the occasion, Evren reminded of the invitations extended to the two Romanian military leaders mentioned above to visit Türkiye, from which he expected a response⁸⁰.

In contrast, on August 17, 1979, the Ceaușescu couple undertook a new visit to Türkiye⁸¹, this time for a day. The Romanian-Turkish conversations once again highlighted mutual interest in the "cause of understanding and cooperation in the Balkans and in Europe"⁸². Beyond the good Romanian-Turkish collaboration in all domains appreciated by both parties, on May 5, 1980, in a telegram sent from Ankara, Turkish Army General Kenan Evren reiterated the perspective of military cooperation, extending an invitation for the Deputy Minister of National Defence and Chief of the General Staff of the Romanian Army to visit Türkiye⁸³.

On April 5-8, 1982, General Kenan Evren, the president of Türkiye, visited Romania. During discussions with his Romanian counterpart, progress and prospects of Romanian-Turkish relations in all domains were emphasized, along with the importance of bilateral collaboration in the Balkans⁸⁴, culminating in a Joint Declaration⁸⁵. Besides the economic objectives visited by the Turkish general, the protocol of the meeting of the Political Executive Committee of the Romanian Communist Party mentioned that the heads of both states had established measures to deepen Romanian-Turkish relations, especially in the context

of the continuity of the European and regional security process post-Helsinki⁸⁶.

To further emphasize Romanian-Turkish friendship, on May 20-23, 1983, Nicolae Ceaușescu visited Türkiye at the invitation of Kenan Evren. Attention was also focused on the situation of nuclear disarmament in the Balkans and the need for normalizing relations between the West and the East⁸⁷. Concurrently, Turkish newspapers like “Turkish Daily News”, “Cumhuriyet”, “Hurriyet”, and “Türkiye” appreciated Ceaușescu’s visit, highlighting the continuation of the strong friendship relationship between Romania and Türkiye⁸⁸.

The way the newspaper “Scântea” portrayed the two reciprocal visits in the early 1980s did not capture concrete elements of progress in Romanian-Turkish relations or propose practical measures or initiatives the two states were expected to undertake in the direction of Balkan security. The information was lacking in substance, formulated in the propagandistic spirit of the era of Nicolae Ceaușescu’s personality cult, to showcase the efforts and extensive activity that the dictator carried out abroad.

In the same vein, during the visit from October 19-21, 1987, when dictator Nicolae Ceaușescu met with Turkish leader Kenan Evren in Ankara, discussions regarding the importance of Romanian-Turkish collaboration for security and stability in the Balkans were resumed, but without any practical proposals⁸⁹. Even in the content of the folder about the visit of the President of the Romanian People’s Republic (RPR) to Türkiye found in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs’ archive, details about this topic were not identified. The documents were limited to the economic sector, potential joint actions in the commercial field, and presenting the progress made between the two countries⁹⁰. At the end of the official discussions, the “strengthening of good relations” between Romania and Türkiye was emphasized⁹¹.

Although Romania continued to maintain good cooperative relations with Türkiye in the 1980s, contemporary sources seem to indicate that bilateral relations did not unfold at the level of the previous decade. The plans and concrete measures that animated the repre-

sentatives of the two states in the 1970s were replaced by courtesy visits to economic and cultural objectives.

The Romanian-Turkish relations in the dynamics of the Cold War reflected the evolution of the post-war international climate analysed in the context of the division of the European continent into two opposing political-military groups: NATO and the Warsaw Treaty Organization. After Stalin’s death, and implicitly the withdrawal of Soviet troops from Romania in 1958, the establishment in Bucharest gradually evolved from conformism to defiance in relations with Moscow, becoming interested in resuming relations with the Western world, especially economically, and culturally and scientifically.

Without escaping from the structures of the socialist bloc, aware that it ensured its political survival, Romania tried to get closer to Türkiye, a NATO member country, itself distraught by US policies in managing the missile crisis of 1962 and that of Cyprus. Beyond the constraints imposed by the rhetoric of the bloc, the common denominator found by both states was the interest in shaping their own foreign policy line and asserting themselves internationally.

The development of Romanian-Turkish bilateral relations gained consistency after Nicolae Ceausescu came to power, and this fact can be seen through the dynamics of exchanges of mutual visits at the level of heads of state, prime ministers, foreign ministers and more. The talks between Romanian and Turkish officials were materialized essentially by signing countless long-term agreements of a scientific, technical, commercial, industrial nature, setting up joint economic commissions, but also exchanges of experience in enterprises to notice the progress made in the two states.

Despite the post-war realities imposed by Europe’s ideological affiliation and bipolar geo-political structure, during the meetings, Romania and Türkiye also tackled more delicate issues such as the military dimension, security and cooperation in the Balkans, their transformation into a zone of peace, aspects of disarmament, and which were material-

ized through mutual support within international forums, in particular UN and CSCE, but also through bilateral cooperation in the area of defence industry, weapons and military equipment. Beyond the status of the two states belonging to blocs with antagonistic political systems, Romania and Türkiye demonstrated until the end of the Cold War that the level of bilateral cooperation and dialogue remained at a high level, supported by common interests.

NOTES

¹ V.V.Kuznețov, Deputy Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Soviet Union.

² The National Archive of Romania (hereinafter ANR), Fond CC of RWP, Foreign Relations, file no. 55/1957, p.3.

³ Laurențiu-Cristian Dumitru, Șerban Pavelescu, *Marea Neagră în timpul Războiului Rece. 1945-1990 (The Black Sea during the Cold War. 1945-1990)*, in the volume “Marea neagră de la «lacul bizantin» la provocările secolului XXI. Culegere de studii”, (“Black Sea from the «Byzantine Lake» to the challenges of the XXI century. Collection of studies”), coordinated by Mihail E. Ionescu, Military Publishing House, Bucharest, 2006, p.332-334.

⁴ The Archives of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (hereinafter AMAE), Fond 220/1957, R.S.R. (The Socialist Republic of Romania)-5, Directorate II, f.p-7.

⁵ Ion Calafeteanu (coord.), *Istoria politicii externe românești în date (History of Romanian Foreign Policy in Data)*, Enciclopedica Publishing House, Bucharest, 2003, p.376.

⁶ AMAE, Fond 220/1957, R.S.R. - 5, Directorate II, p.27-32.

⁷ AMAE, Fond 220/1964, R.P.R. (People’s Republic of Romania)-5, Directorate II, p.1.

⁸ AMAE, Fond 220/1966, Türkiye 1, Directorate II, Foreign Relations, p.26-36.

⁹ AMAE, Fond 220, R.P.R.-5, Directorate II, f. 2-3.

¹⁰ AMAE, Fond 220, Türkiye /1961, Türkiye, Directorate II, Foreign Relations, f.8.

¹¹ *Ibidem*.

¹² *Ibidem*, f.9.

¹³ *Ibidem*, f.10.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*.

¹⁵ *Ibidem*.

¹⁶ “Scântea”, Year XXXI, No. 5570, June 25, 1962, p.2.

¹⁷ Since 1963, cultural exchange protocols have been concluded annually between Romania and Türkiye. See AMAE, Fond 220/1966, Türkiye 1, Directorate II, Foreign Relations, p.1-3.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*, p.4-8.

¹⁹ Süleyman Demirel (1924-2015), Turkish politician. He was Prime Minister of Türkiye for seven terms from 1965 to 1993, and President from 1993 to 2000.

²⁰ Corneliu Mănescu was nominally invited by Prime Minister Süleyman Demirel to Türkiye and had an important role in discussions with the Turkish side on issues of economic cooperation (oil, iron ore, petrochemicals and transport). AMAE, Fond 220/1966, Türkiye 1, Directorate II, Foreign Relations, p.4-8.

²¹ AMAE, Fond 220/1966, Türkiye 1, Directorate II, Foreign Relations, Volume II, p.45-49.

²² AMAE, Fond 220/1966, Türkiye 1, Directorate II, Foreign Relations, p.159-168.

²³ *Ibidem*.

²⁴ *Ibidem*.

²⁵ *Ibidem*.

²⁶ AMAE, Fond 220/1967, Special Files, Türkiye 2, p.1-2.

²⁷ AMAE, Fond 220/1968, R.S.R.-5, Directorate II, p.14.

²⁸ *Ibidem*.

²⁹ AMAE, Fond 220/1967, Special Files, Türkiye 2, p.1-2.

³⁰ AMAE, Fond 220/1968, R.S.R.-5, Directorate II-a, p.21-23.

³¹ AMAE, Fond 220/1967, Türkiye, Directorate II, Foreign Relations, p.159.

³² *Ibidem*, p.158.

³³ AMAE, Fond 220/1967, Special Files, Türkiye 2, f. 151-153.

³⁴ *Ibidem*, f.154-159.

³⁵ AMAE, Fond 220/1967, Türkiye, Directorate II, Foreign Relations, p.159.

³⁶ AMAE, Fond 220/1967, Special Files, Türkiye 2, p.151-153.

³⁷ “Scântea”, Year XXXVII, no. 7462, September 14, 1967, p.1.

³⁸ “Scântea”, Year I XXXVII, no. 7466, September 18, 1967, p.1-4.

³⁹ AMAE, Fond 220/1968, Türkiye 4, part I, Special Files, p.11-13.

⁴⁰ AMAE, Fond 220/1968, Türkiye 4, part II, Special Files, p.63-65.

⁴¹ AMAE, Special Files, Fond 220/1968, Türkiye 4, Volume II, f. 178-184

⁴² “Scântea”, Year XXXIII, no. 8015, March 25, 1969, p.3.

⁴³ "Scântea", Year XXXIII, no. 8016, March 26, 1969, p. 3.

⁴⁴ *Ibidem*.

⁴⁵ "Scântea", Year XXXIII, no. 8020, March 30, 1969, p.1-3.

⁴⁶ "Scântea", Year XXXVIII, no. 8013, March 23, 1969, p.1.

⁴⁷ "Scântea", Year XXXVIII, no. 8014, March 24, 1969, p.1.

⁴⁸ "Scântea", Year XXXIX, no. 8399, April 17, 1970, p.1-3.

⁴⁹ "Scântea", Year XXXIX, no. 8400, April 18, 1970, p.5.

⁵⁰ Among these, from the first half of the 70s, we selectively mention Nicolae Ceausescu's visits to the West – France, Austria, Iceland, Canada, USA, Finland, Belgium, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Italy, West Germany –, but also the visits of Western heads of state and government to Bucharest from Austria, Finland, Holland, Israel, the visit of Margaret Thatcher, Henry Kissinger, Jacques Chirac, Gerard Ford etc.

⁵¹ Mioara Anton, *Când maverick a încetat să fie maverick. Nicolae Ceaușescu și Pactul de la Varșovia (1980-1990), When maverick stopped being maverick. Nicolae Ceaușescu and the Warsaw Pact (1980-1990)* in the volume "Revoluția din 1989. Învinși și învingători" ("The Revolution of 1989. Losers and Winners"), coordinated by Anneli Ute Gabanyi, Alexandru Muraru, Andrei Muraru, Daniel Sandru, Polirom Publishing House, Iași, 2020, p.90-100.

⁵² *July 30, 1971, Moscow. Telegram from the First Secretary of the Romanian Embassy in the USSR, Ilie Georgescu, to the First Directorate for Information Relations received by the U.S. Department of State regarding the convening of a special conference of Warsaw Treaty member countries* in the volume "Documente Diplomatice Române. Seria a III-a. România și Tratatul de la Varșovia. Conferințele miniștrilor Afacerilor Externe și ale adjuncților lor (1966-1991)" (Romanian Diplomatic Documents. Series III. Romania and the Warsaw Treaty. Conferences of the Ministers of Foreign Affairs and their Deputies (1966-1991), Volume edited by Mioara Anton, Alpha MDN Publishing House, Bucharest, 2009, p.325-326 (hereinafter to be quoted under the logo *DDR, Romania and the Warsaw Treaty*).

⁵³ Central State Archive of Bulgaria, Sofia, Fond 1-B, File 2499, p.10.

⁵⁴ *Ibidem*.

⁵⁵ January 20, 1973, Bucharest. Summary of the talks held by the First Secretary of the Central Committee of the CPSU, L.I. Brezhnev, with the Ministers of Foreign Affairs, regarding the stage of nego-

tiations of the USSR with France, West Germany and the USA, on European security issues in *DDR, Romania and the Warsaw Treaty*, p.375-376.

⁵⁶ It is about the fact that the Romanian diplomacy had an initiative regarding the rules of procedure of the Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe that were not previously brought to the attention of the Soviets. Romanian Ambassador Valentin Lipatti mentions in his memories that the "irritation" of the Soviets was caused by the fact that "we had not consulted them beforehand on the procedural document, as we were supposed to do, according to the ritual existing under the Warsaw Treaty". See, Valentin Lipatti "În tranșeele Europei. Amintirile unui negociator" ("In the trenches of Europe. Memories of a negotiator"), Military Publishing House, Bucharest, 1993, p.27.

⁵⁷ January 20, 1973, Bucharest. Summary of the talks held by the First Secretary of the Central Committee of the CPSU, L.I. Brezhnev, with the Ministers of Foreign Affairs, regarding the stage of negotiations of the USSR with France, West Germany and the USA, on European security issues, in *DDR, Romania and the Warsaw Treaty*, p.375-376.

⁵⁸ AMAE, Fond 220/1971, Türkiye 5, Volume 2, Directorate I, Foreign Relations, p.21-22.

⁵⁹ AMAE, Fond 220/1972, R.S.R.-5, Directorate I, Foreign Relations, Volume I, p.58-60.

⁶⁰ *Ibidem*.

⁶¹ *Ibidem*.

⁶² *Ibidem*, p.68 -72.

⁶³ AMAE, Fond 221/1974, f. 1-2.

⁶⁴ *Ibidem*, p.13.

⁶⁵ "Scântea", Year XLV, no. 10270, August 28, 1975, p.1-3.

⁶⁶ *Ibidem*.

⁶⁷ "Scântea", Year XLV, no. 10525, June 23, 1976, p.1.

⁶⁸ *Ibidem*, p.3.

⁶⁹ Beyond the Balkan security aspects, an important point of the talks between the two heads of state remained cooperation in the technical-scientific, economic, commercial and cultural fields, unanimously assessed as having made "significant progress" in technical-scientific, economic and cultural cooperation.

⁷⁰ The alliance was to consist of Romania, Yugoslavia, Bulgaria, Türkiye, Greece and Albania.

⁷¹ August 3, 1976, Note of conversation on the occasion of the meeting of Comrade Nicolae Ceaușescu with Comrade Leonid Ilyich Brezhnev, Secretary General of the Central Committee of the CPSU, in *DDR, Romania and the Warsaw Treaty*, p.490.

⁷² *Ibidem*.

⁷³ *Ibidem*.

⁷⁴ AMAE, Fond 220/B, 1977, Türkiye – R.S.R., p.6.

⁷⁵ *Ibidem*, p.29.

⁷⁶ *Ibidem*, p.30.

⁷⁷ Central State Archive of Bulgaria, Sofia, Fond 1-B, File 2499, f.21.

⁷⁸ *Ibidem*, f.21.

⁷⁹ AMAE, Fond 211/1978/Türkiye – R.S.R., p.1.

⁸⁰ *Ibidem*, p.1.

⁸¹ In this context, a synthesis was elaborated on the “continuous upward evolution” of Romanian-Turkish relations from the perspective of economic cooperation and trade. See AMAE, Fond 20/1980, Türkiye, p.1-8.

⁸² “Scânteia”, An XLIX, Nr. 11505, August 18, 1979, p.1.

⁸³ AMAE, Fond 220/1980, Türkiye, p.28.

⁸⁴ “Scânteia”, Year LI, Nr. 12323, April 6, 1982, p.1.

⁸⁵ “Scânteia”, Year LI, Nr. 12326, April 9, 1982, p.1.

⁸⁶ ANR, Fond CC of RCP, Chancellery Department, Volume 1, File 20/1982, p.9-10.

⁸⁷ “Scânteia”, Year LII, no. 12672, May 21, 1983, p.3.

⁸⁸ *Ibidem*, p.2.

⁸⁹ “Scânteia”, Year LVII, no. 14047, October 20, 1987, p.1-3.

⁹⁰ AMAE, Fond 220/1987, Türkiye, p.22-48; 75-79.

⁹¹ “Scânteia”, Year LVII, no. 14048, October 21, 1987, p.1.